

SPEAKING-IN-CLASS ANXIETY OF ENGLISH-MAJORED UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The feeling of anxiety is commonly expressed in a language classroom by second/foreign language learners, and this feeling is considered to affect learners' speaking performance. The present study was conducted to investigate levels of in-class speaking anxiety experienced by the first-year English-majored students at the School of Foreign Languages, Thai Nguyen university and find out the types of in-class speaking activities that provoke or reduce students' speaking anxiety. The research subjects were 101 students majoring in English in the two programs: English Education and English Language Programs. A survey questionnaire was employed to collect the data. The descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that the students' anxiety about speaking English in classroom was at the high level. The findings also showed that the activities with high self-exposure requirement were the most anxiety-evoking to students. On the other hand, the activities that give students a chance to work in pairs or in groups; especially in class games caused the least anxiety to them. Finally, the pedagogical implications for understanding second/foreign language anxiety and for enhancing learners' communication abilities in the target language were discussed.

Key words: Speaking-in-class anxiety, SFL English-majored students, fear of negative evaluation, communication apprehension, test anxiety.

1 INTRODUCTION

Foreign language anxiety is one of the important barriers which may cause various difficulties for the language learners. This problem limits learners' linguistic improvement, limits learner's abilities and also diminishes potential performance of the learners. A student, if confronted with some failure in speaking English, would remain silent more frequently when being required to speak; some even lack the courage to try to open their mouths and speak, or stumble and stammer when they speak. Even though many teachers are aware of the problem relating to students' anxiety, they do not take that big issue into account. When learners enroll in different language courses, they are offered only to develop their English but most of the times no systematic steps are taken to reduce their anxiety. As a result, learners who have English speaking anxiety face difficulties when they are required to speak even after learning the language for a long time.

Over the last decades, a great body of studies has been conducted on language anxiety in foreign language and second/ foreign language learning in general (Scovel, 1978; Horwitz, Horwitz, &

Cope, 1986; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991a, 1991b, 1991c; etc.) and in foreign language speaking skill in particular (Woodrow, 2006; Liu, 2006; Lu & Liu, 2011; Ozturk & Gurbuz, 2014; Salem & Dyyar, 2014). However, contrary to what is happening abroad, fewer studies in Vietnam have been conducted and acknowledged the effects of anxiety on foreign language learning. Only some empirical studies have touched on the sources of anxiety (Tran et al., 2013, Nguyen, 2014), and none of them has focused on the English-majored students of Thai Nguyen university. Therefore, the present research aimed to investigate speaking-in-class anxiety with the main focus on the second-year English-majored students at the School of Foreign Languages, Thai Nguyen university.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Foreign language anxiety and Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope's model

Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope (1986: 128) provided three “useful conceptual building blocks” for a description of foreign language anxiety; namely communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety. Communication apprehension is defined as “a type of shyness characterized by fear of or anxiety about communicating with people” (Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986: 127). It refers to an individual's level of fear or anxiety associated with either real or anticipated oral communication with another person or persons. Test anxiety refers to “a type of performance resulting from a fear of failure” (Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986: 127). Of all the tests and quizzes, oral ones are especially anxiety-provoking since anxious students probably manifest both communication apprehension and test anxiety in this kind of test (Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986). Finally, fear of negative evaluation is the “apprehension about others' evaluations, avoidance of evaluative situations, and the expectation that others would evaluate oneself negatively” (Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986: 128).

2.2 Speaking as a source of anxiety

Compared to other language skills such as listening, writing and reading, a certain amount of research has supported studies in which speaking or communicating in the foreign language classroom has been the most crucial source of anxiety (Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986; Liu, 1989; Young, 1990; Phillips, 1992, Cheng, Horwitz, & Schallert, 1999). In its simplest form, speaking can be defined as a productive and an interactive skill, which goes through four separate cognitive stages: conceptualization, formulation, articulation and self-monitoring (Levelt, cited in Pawlak, 2015). This process is completed in a very short time so it is impossible for the speaker to control all the stages. Therefore, the successful completion of the stages depends on automaticity, and so the lack of automaticity might cause students' difficulty in speaking and make them feel anxious (Huang, 1998).

According to Shumin (1997), learning to speak a foreign language effectively requires to develop communicative competence. Communicative competence is defined as the ability to “convey and interpret messages and to negotiate meanings interpersonally within specific contexts” (Brown, 1994: 227). Analyzing the elements of communicative competence enables one to identify the underlying components of second language speaking proficiency that learners may find difficult

(Shumin, 1997). The first difficulty comes from the complexity of communicative competence, in which several other types of competence are involved: grammatical competence (learners' mastery of certain grammatical elements), discourse competence (learners' knowledge of conveying messages as a coherent whole), socio-linguistic competence (learners' ability to decide appropriate uses of language in accordance with the elements of the social context in which it is used) and strategic competence (learners' ability to maintain communication despite some deficiencies that they may have). Other difficulties may come from the features of speaking. Speakers have to complete the process of speech under time pressure, which increases the risk of making mistakes. When speakers have difficulty in correcting their mistakes, listeners cannot understand the message, and this can break communication. Another feature can be connected with the listening side of speaking, which may be a source of difficulty. That is, speaking is a reciprocal skill in which interlocutors take turns as speakers and listeners. When the listener has difficulty in understanding what the speaker says, they cannot negotiate meaning. This can lead the listener to avoid speaking due to fear of misunderstanding when it is his or her turn to listen. To sum up, the complexity of communicative competence, which requires learners to acquire four different types of competence, as well as certain features of speaking, may cause learners to have difficulties and feel anxious in oral communication.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Participants of the study

The population of the study consisted of 101 second-year English-majored students, both male and female.

3.2 Instruments

The author adapted two questionnaires developed by Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope (1986) and Young (1990). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part 1, In-Class English Speaking Anxiety Scale (adapted FLCAS, Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986); Part 2, Speaking Anxiety Towards In-Class Activities (adapted from Young, 1990)

3.3 Data collection procedures

The questionnaire was administered when students were on week 6 of the first semester of the second year 2016-2017. The questionnaires were delivered to the students in their classroom in the break time.

3.4 Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were used in the present study, which include the calculation of frequency and percentage of students' responses.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 In-class English speaking anxiety

This section involves statistical methods used in order to analyze the data obtained from 101 second-year SFL students majoring in English through the first part of the speaking anxiety questionnaire. The levels of in-class speaking anxiety is indicated on a five-point rating scale, ranging from “Strongly disagree” valued as 1, “Disagree” valued as 2, “Neither Disagree nor Agree” valued as 3, “Agree” valued as 4 and “Strongly agree” valued as 5.

Table 4.1: Students’ responses to ICESA scale

Item No	Items	Percentage (%)				
		Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither disagree nor agree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
1	I never have self-confidence when speaking English in class.	2.0	8.9	34.7	39.6	14.9
2	I tend to tremble when called to answer the question in class.	3.0	20.8	36.6	30.7	8.9
3	I wouldn’t bother me to take extra English speaking classes.*	16.8	45.5	32.7	4.0	1.0
4	I feel uncomfortable when speaking English in front of my classmates.	2.0	5.9	24.8	37.6	29.7
5	I get worried when I have to speak English without prior preparation in class.	1.0	2.0	14.9	42.6	39.6
6	When I feel nervous, I tend to forget what I have intended to speak.	0.0	10.9	28.7	38.6	21.8
7	I always feel my heart pounding when I’m going to be called on in English class.	3.0	20.8	34.7	29.7	11.9
8	I tend to get nervous and confused when doing speaking tasks in class.	3.0	24.8	33.7	26.7	11.9
9	I tend to get nervous when asked to answer questions without prior preparation.	0.0	3.0	12.9	41.6	42.6
10	I am frightened when I don’t	1.0	26.7	31.7	32.7	7.9

Item No	Items	Percentage (%)				
		Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither disagree nor agree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
	understand what the teacher is saying in English.					
11	Even if I am well prepared for English class, I feel anxious about it.	2.0	55.4	32.7	8.9	1.0
12	I feel confident when speaking English in class.	15.8	54.5	23.8	5.0	1.0
13	I feel more tense and nervous in my English speaking class than in my other classes.	3.0	12.9	37.6	36.6	9.9
14	I feel nervous to speak English no matter how difficult or easy a speaking task is.	5.9	34.7	40.6	13.9	5.0
15	Whether I will be worried in English class or not depends on the difficulty of the task assigned.	6.9	16.8	34.7	26.7	14.9
16	I feel bad about my speaking ability when speaking in the English class because my English is not good.	5.0	11.9	30.7	34.7	17.8
17	I feel uncomfortable speaking English in class even though I have good preparation	5.0	25.7	32.7	23.8	12.9
18	I dislike participating in pairwork and group discussions in speaking class.	14.9	31.7	35.6	13.9	4.0
19	I am tense and nervous using English in pairwork and group discussions in speaking class.	10.9	58.4	23.8	4.0	3.0
20	Using English in a pairwork and group discussion with unfamiliar students makes me tense and nervous.	7.9	57.4	26.7	6.9	1.0
21	While having an English-speaking test I am afraid that my English teacher will correct every mistake I make.	5.0	36.6	44.6	12.9	1.0

Item No	Items	Percentage (%)				
		Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither disagree nor agree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
22	I usually feel relaxed while having an English-speaking test.*	3.0	11.9	33.7	34.7	16.8
23	The more I study for the English test, the more confused I get.	3.0	37.6	48.5	8.9	2.0
24	I do not worry about making mistakes when having a speaking English test.*	2.0	7.9	33.7	33.7	18.8
25	I don't worry about making mistakes when speaking English.*	2.0	5.9	11.9	52.5	27.7
26	I always feel that the other students speak English better than I do.	4.0	13.9	28.7	40.6	12.9
27	I am afraid that the other students will laugh at me when I speak English.	4.0	11.9	38.6	40.6	5.0
28	I feel embarrassed to volunteer answers in my English class.	3.0	18.8	37.6	33.7	6.9
29	I always worry about the consequences of failing my English class.	1.0	5.0	30.7	40.6	22.8
30	I feel that my English-speaking class moves very quickly and I am afraid of getting left behind.	2.0	5.0	31.7	48.5	12.9
Average Percentage		4.6	22.8	31.5	28.2	12.9

* For items 3, 22, 24, 25, values 1&2 mean a high level of anxiety, and values 4&5 mean no anxiety. Therefore, they are reverse scored before calculating the total score.

Table 4.1 reports the data obtained from the students' responses with percentages of students selecting each alternative. Although the data shown in table 4.1 reveals slightly different percentages of responses, it is clearly seen that while a certain number of students reported to have no anxiety in English speaking classrooms, there was still a significant percentage of students choosing Values 4 and 5 as reporting to experience anxiety in English speaking classrooms. Therefore, students' in-class English speaking anxiety can be categorized into three levels. Values 1 and 2 could be categorized as no anxiety; Value 3 indicates that the participants

manifest a low level of anxiety; and Values 4 and 5 consider the participants experience a high level of anxiety. The data, therefore, is presented on another way as can be seen on Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Students’ level of in-class speaking anxiety

Opinions	Percentage (%)	Anxiety level
Strongly disagree and disagree (Values 1 & 2)	27.4	None
Neither disagree nor agree (Value 3)	31.5	Low
Agree and Strongly Agree (Values 4 & 5)	41.1	High

The result of the descriptive analysis shown in Table 4.2 indicates that only 27.4% of the surveyed students reported to be anxiety-free in English speaking classroom. On the other hand, approximately 73% of the students manifested from a low level of anxiety to a high level of anxiety in English speaking classrooms. This finding addresses Research Question 1. As a result, it can be concluded that approximately two third of the second-year SFL English-majored students experience anxiety from low to high level in which nearly 50% exhibit high level of speaking-in-class anxiety.

4.2 Anxiety towards in-class activities

The second research question this study aims to answer is what in-class activities provoke or reduce English speaking anxiety in classroom. The data were analyzed by computing the percentages of students’ responses on 20 in-class activities in the second part of the questionnaire. Table 4.3 below calculated the percentage of students’ responses to different in-class activities.

Table 4.3: In-class speaking activities

Activity No	Activity types	Percentage (%)				
		Very Relaxed (1)	Moderately Relaxed (2)	Neither Relaxed nor Anxious (3)	Moderately Anxious (4)	Very Anxious (5)
1	Work in groups of 3 or 4.	30.7	33.7	28.7	3.0	4.0
2	Compete in class games by teams.	56.4	27.7	8.9	5.9	1.0
3	Open discussion based on volunteer participation.	13.9	46.5	28.7	9.9	1.0

Activity No	Activity types	Percentage (%)				
		Very Relaxed (1)	Moderately Relaxed (2)	Neither Relaxed nor Anxious (3)	Moderately Anxious (4)	Very Anxious (5)
4	Speak individually with the teacher in the class.	5.0	14.9	44.6	23.8	11.9
5	Repeat as a class after the teacher.	10.9	34.7	32.7	20.8	1.0
6	Listen to teacher's questions and respond individually.	6.9	29.7	27.7	34.7	1.0
7	Role play a situation spontaneously in front of the class.	0.0	12.9	36.6	32.7	17.8
8	Do speaking exercises in the book individually.	10.9	39.6	36.6	10.9	2.0
9	Repeat individually after the teacher.	5.9	34.7	41.6	14.9	3.0
10	Read orally in class.	9.9	37.6	27.7	21.8	3.0
11	Interview each other in pairs.	14.9	48.5	24.8	10.9	1.0
12	Work in groups of two and prepare a skit.	15.8	44.6	22.8	13.9	3.0
13	Role play a situation.	10.9	27.7	37.6	20.8	3.0
14	Present a prepared dialogue in front of the class.	7.9	23.8	34.7	29.7	4.0
15	Speak in front of the class.	5.0	21.8	26.7	33.7	12.9
16	Work on projects (i.e., newspapers, filmstrips, photo albums).	12.9	25.7	34.7	18.8	7.9
17	Make an oral presentation or skit in front of the class.	1.0	16.8	29.7	34.7	17.8

From Table 4.3, it can be concluded that in-class English speaking activities are categorized into three main groups: Activities valued as 1&2 are those causing no anxiety to students, Activities valued as 3 are those causing less anxiety to students and activities valued as 4&5 are those

provoking the most students' in-class speaking anxiety. The detailed description of each in-class activity regarding three levels are demonstrated in Figure 4.1.

As can be seen from figure 4.1, the top three in-class activities that cause the highest anxiety level to students are Activities 17, 7, and 15. On the contrary, several activities that cause less or no anxiety to students in English speaking class are Activities 2, 1, 11, 3, 12, and 8. The detailed representation and analysis of those activities are included in table 3.8 and 3.9 below.

Table 4.4 demonstrates the highest anxiety activities which began with the one having the highest frequency of "Moderately anxious" (Value 4) and "Very anxious" (Value 5).

Figure 4.1: SFL students' perceptions of 17 in-class activities

Table 4.4: In-class speaking activities with high anxiety

Activity No	Activity types	Percentage (%)
17	Make an oral presentation or skit in front of the class.	52.5
7	Role play a situation spontaneously in front of the class.	50.5
15	Speak in front of the class.	46.5
4	Speak individually with the teacher in class	35.6
6	Listen to teacher's questions and respond individually.	35.6

According to table 4.4, the two activities which provoke anxiety most are "Make an oral presentation or skit in in front of the class." (Activity 17) with the percentage of 52.5%. The second anxiety-provoking speaking activity belongs to "Role play a situation spontaneously in

front of the class” (50.5%). The reason why more than half of the students reported their moderate and high anxiety level on these activities may reflect the fact that making an oral presentation rarely occurs in everyday communication. It requires one to give a speech to a large audience. Therefore, it calls upon different communication skills, which the students have not been taught and may be afraid of. These two activities are followed by “*speak in front of the class*” (Activity 15) (46.5%). The same number of students reported a relatively high level of anxiety when “*speaking individually with the teacher in class*” (Activity 4) and “Listen to teacher’s questions and respond individually” (Activity 6) (35.6%). Interestingly, what these activities have in common is that they all require high-exposure. In other words, these findings show that students feel the most anxious when they have to make a speech in the foreign language in front of a large group, especially when they have no idea about what they are going to say or in other words, they have no preparation before hand. This finding is similar with the one found in Young (1990: 547). In his study, Young (1990) concluded that “the real anxiety-evoking situation is having to speak or perform in front of others” (p. 546).

Table 4.5 below demonstrates the arrangement of activities making students comfortable, which began with the one having the highest frequency of “Moderately relaxed” (Value 2) and “Very relaxed” (Value 1).

Table 4.5: In-class speaking activities with low anxiety

Activity No	Activity types	Percentage (%)
2	Compete in class games by teams	84.2
1	Work in groups of 3 or 4	64.4
11	Interview each other in pairs.	63.4
3	Open discussion based on volunteer participation	60.4
12	Work in groups of two and prepare a skit.	60.4
8	Do exercises in the book.	50.5

Table 4.5 reveals that the highest percentage of students reported that they felt comfortable and relaxed when participating in class games (84.2%). In addition, “*Working in groups*” (Activities 1, & 12), “*Interview each other in pairs.*” (Activity 11) and “*Open discussion based on volunteer participation*” (Activity 3) are the practices that make students feel most relaxed in speaking class. In addition, more than half of the students reported to be relaxed when they do exercises in the book. This finding is in contrast with Young’s (1990) in which he found those activities moderately provoke anxiety among the student participants.

To sum up, the findings of the Speaking Anxiety toward in-class activities show that a higher level of anxiety exists specially for those in-class practices involving speaking and with a high self-exposure requirement (Activities 17, 7, 15, 4, 6, 14). On the contrary, the activities which are judged as more comfort-producing are those ones where students are individually without being spotlighted in front of the class and given the opportunity to work in pairs or small groups

(Activities 2, 1, 11, 3, 12). In other words, this finding indicate that cooperative activities and group learning are considered the effective and efficient learning ways to reduce students' fear of self-exposure since students can express themselves in the name of the whole group instead of individuals.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

The present study has reported on the research findings of students' anxiety about speaking English in classrooms. First, based on the findings of the present study, the descriptive analysis shows that the second-year SFL students majoring in English experience English speaking anxiety in their classrooms at the "high" level. Second, most of students feel worried in those activities with a high self-exposure requirement. Among those activities, any that requires students to make an oral presentation or perform spontaneously in front of the classmates turn out to be in-class practices which put the student in a very stressful situation. On the other hand, the findings show that students feel more relaxed when they work or play games in pairs or in groups, and when they have the opportunity to practice speaking without being spotlighted in front of the rest of the class.

Given that language anxiety can exercise detrimental influence on second/foreign language learning and communication in the target language, it is important that language teachers not only recognize that anxiety is a major cause of students' lack of success in the new language but also assist them to tackle the feelings of unease and discomfort. ESL/EFL language teachers should acknowledge the existence of the feeling of anxiety in learning and particularly speaking English language and then should take appropriate techniques to reduce it. They should make students feel comfortable by avoiding activities which threaten students' self-esteem or which require high exposure is very important. Working in small groups, discussing interesting topics, and playing English games as well are good activities that allow students to know each other and to practice the foreign language without any fear.

6 LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

In terms of methodology, it would be more beneficial if the participants were selected from different types of universities and years of study. To do this, other findings relevant to in-class speaking anxiety might merge from these participants with the hope that it would be more generalizable to a larger group of Vietnamese university students. In addition, the anxiety involving other English learning skills such as listening, reading, or writing should have been investigated as well.

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